

ReadMe

This is documentation for how to run image analysis pipeline to track Lacl foci over time course and then extract ROIs from cells meeting tracking criteria. Individual cells then get cropped and organized into labeled folders for manual visual analysis for enrichment. If a brightfield image of the whole field of view is taken, the pipeline can overlay track number onto the image to identify which cell tracks are connected to.

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Image Analysis Workflow Overview:

1. Open time series image in FIJI and set lookup tables as desired
2. Run PreprocessingArea.ijm in FIJI to set area of image for tracking
3. Run FIJI plugin TrackMate (params below)
4. Run ExtractROI.py in FIJI
5. Run ImageAnalysis.sh in terminal

Step-by-Step of Workflow:

1. Open time series image in FIJI and set lookup tables as desired

Time series image should be already deconvolved (if using) and made into a maximum intensity projection. Open in FIJI and set lookup tables of image channels as desired for output.

2. Run PreprocessingArea.ijm in FIJI to set area of image for tracking.

This allows for setting boundary of tracked image to ensure ROIs are not too near to the boundary of the image. Can adjust coordinates as desired for image size. In this case the following coordinates were used for all 1024x1024 pixel images.

```
//setTool("rectangle");  
makeRectangle(50, 50, 924, 924);
```

3. Run FIJI plugin TrackMate

This is the plugin used for tracking Lacl foci. Go to Plugins>Tracking>TrackMate to open TrackMate window. The following parameters were used for tracking:

1. Image Parameters
X: 50 to 973
Y: 50 to 973
Z: 0 to 0
T: 0 to 29

2. Select a detector: LoG detector
3. Settings for detector:
 1. Detect in channel: select correct channel containing Lacl
 2. Estimated object diameter: 0.5 micron
 3. Quality threshold: 100

*can use Preview button to visualize detected spots on open image
4. Initial thresholding: select all (will use specific filters after tracking)
5. Set filters on spots:
 1. Contrast chX (whichever channel you are tracking in): set above and place lower limit at the beginning of the plateau. Can visually see on the open image to ensure capturing Lacl well. This will vary image to image depending on contrast of Lacl spots and background.
6. Select a tracker: LAP Tracker
7. Settings for tracker:
 1. Frame to frame linking: 1 micron
 2. Track segment gap closing: do not allow gap closing (do not check box)
 3. Track segment splitting: do not allowing splitting (do not check box)
 4. Track segment merging: do not allow merging (do not check box)
8. Set filters on tracks:
 1. Track displacement: Below 1.8 micron
 2. Track start: Below 1 (must be identifiable in T=0)
 3. Track stop: Above 20 (must be trackable until at least the 20th frame)
9. Open "Tracks" tab at bottom. Select all in "Spots" tab, export to CSV and save as "export.csv" in desired directory. Switch to "Tracks" tab and select all tracks, save as "export_tracks.csv" in desired directory.
10. Return to main TrackMate window, advance twice. Select an action: Export spots to IJ ROIs; execute for selection (track info now in ROI Manager)

4. Run ExtractROI.py in FIJI

Open ExtractROI.py and run script through FIJI. Will prompt to select directory, choose desired working directory. **DO NOT TOUCH FIJI as script opens, writes, and closes continuously. May lead to closing wrong image.**

5. Run ImageAnalysis.sh in terminal

As indicated in ImageAnalysis.sh, place the necessary scripts in a folder on the system and edit corresponding working directory paths in the script. Scripts needed are:

1. imageSort.R
2. GenerateStack.py
3. Track_Coordinates.R (only if want to label brightfield image)
4. BF_label.ijm (only if want to label brightfield image)

Copy ImageAnalysis.sh into directory with ExtractROI.py outputs. Open terminal and run in this directory.

```
{bash}
```

```
bash ImageAnalysis.sh
```

Note: subscripts will open new instances of FIJI and prompt you for directory, so do not leave script while running.

Done.